

Table 1

Template for the Specification of Analytical Goals/Questions.

ID	Analytical Goal/Question	Priority
AR1	Monitor the evolution of vibrations by sensor and when they pass their threshold	Should
AR2	Monitor the evolution of spindle electrical current and speed, and when they pass their threshold.	Should
AR3	Monitor the evolution of speed rate	Should
AR4	Analyze the average values of velocity and acceleration vibrations, temperature, spindle rotation and electrical current, and speed rate	Should
AR5	Identify the material that causes the most anomalies	Must
AR6	Identify the tool that causes the most anomalies	Must
AR7	Identify the tool x material pair that causes the most anomalies	Must
AR8	Determine which sensor registers the most anomalies	Must
AR9	Determine how many anomalies were caused by the motor	Must
AR10	Calculate the average time between anomalies	Must
AR11	Calculate the average time it takes to resume work after an anomaly	Must
AR12	Calculate the total time the machine was stopped	Must
AR13	Analyze the average machine occupancy	Could
AR14	Determine the average number of materials cut in a day	Could
AR15	Determine the number of tool changes in a day	Could
AR16	Calculate the total tool change time	Could
AR17	Identify the most used tool sequence	Could
AR18	Identify the tool that is used the longest	Could
AR19	Analyze the average speed values, electrical current and rotation values by type of material	Could
AR20	Analyze the average values of speed, electrical current and rotation per tool	Could
AR21	Determine which operation takes the longest per type of material and tool	Could